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SHIGELLOSIS INCIDENCE TRENDS IN UKRAINE IN 2021-2024

Abstract:

The work analyzed current information on the dynamics of the incidence of shigellosis in Ukraine in the period 2021-2024. Shigellosis remains a pressing public health problem both in the world and in Ukraine. Shigellosis is of particular importance in low- and middle-income countries, where infectious diarrheal diseases significantly affect the morbidity and mortality of the population Tourists, visitors to mass events, and people living in unsanitary conditions are at risk of infection.

Анотація:

В роботі аналізувалась актуальна інформація щодо динаміки захворюваності на шигельоз в період 2021-2024 роки в Україні. Шигельоз залишається однією з актуальних проблем громадського здоров'я як у світі, так і в Україні. Особливе значення шигельоз набуває в країнах із низьким та середнім рівнем доходу, де інфекційні діарейні захворювання суттєво впливають на захворюваність і смертність населення. В зоні ризику зараження перебувають туристи, відвідувачі масових заходів та населення, що проживає в антисанітарних умовах.

Ключові слова: шигельоз, антисанітарія, поширеність, кишкова інфекція

Key words: shigellosis, unsanitary conditions, prevalence, intestinal infection

Introduction: Shigellosis is an acute diarrheal infection caused by enteroinvasive Gram-negative, facultatively anaerobic bacillus of the genus *Shigella* [1]. It is estimated that approximately 165 million cases of shigellosis are reported worldwide annually [2].

Materials and methods: we conducted a literature review based on articles published in PubMed databases over the past 5 years and official data from the Public Health Center of Ukraine. We analyzed current information on the dynamics of shigellosis incidence in Ukraine in 2021-2024.

The purpose of the work :The goal was to analyze scientific works, literary sources, official sources of the Public Health Center of Ukraine and determine the dynamics of the incidence of shigellosis in the period 2021-2024 in Ukraine.

Topicality: Worldwide, most cases of shigellosis are caused by *Shigella sonnei* or *S. flexneri*, although *S. boydii* and *S. dysenteriae* also contribute to the spread of gastrointestinal disease in endemic regions and can cause infectious gastrointestinal disease in travelers returning from India and Africa [4]. *Shigella* includes 4 species, each representing 1 of 4 serogroups A through D. Each serogroup includes 1 or more serotypes with unique biochemical characteristics and virulence. *Shigella* serogroups consist of the following:

Serogroup A: *Shigella dysenteriae* (15 serotypes);

Serogroup B: *Shigella flexneri* (19 serotypes and subserotypes);

Serogroup C: *Shigella boydii* (20 serotypes);

Serogroup D: *Shigella sonnei* (1 serotype) [1].

Transmission of the infection occurs through the fecal-oral route - directly from person to person. In this regard, shigellosis is more often recorded in conditions that favor fecal-oral spread of the pathogen, in particular in preschool institutions or in places with limited access to centralized water supply [2]. Waterborne transmission is a less common route of transmission, accounting for up to 15% of all sporadic cases of shigellosis [5].

Shigella is less susceptible to destruction by stomach acid than other bacteria as it passes through the stomach. After leaving the stomach, *Shigella* multiplies in the small intestine and enters the large intestine. In the colon, they secrete virulence factors that cause severe inflammation and mediate enterotoxic effects, promoting colonization and invasion of the colonic epithelium. *Shigella* produces 3 enterotoxins that cause watery or bloody diarrhea and symptoms associated with infection, such as tenesmus, malaise, and fever. The dynamics of shigellosis transmission show strong annual and multi-year cycles, as well as seasonality [6]. Shigellosis infection peaks in the summer months. Observations have shown that the incidence is highest in hot and dry weather, which is explained by water scarcity and limited hygiene measures [7].

Outbreaks of shigellosis usually occur when consuming foods that have undergone manual handling, limited heat treatment, or raw foods [8]. Shigellosis outbreaks are more common during military operations and natural disasters, which lead to unsanitary living conditions, overcrowding, and poor

sanitation. It is also noteworthy that rising global temperatures are increasing the risk of diarrheal diseases, such as shigellosis [1]. Cases of asymptomatic carriage also play an important role in the spread of infection, which complicates epidemiological control.

Severe shigellosis can occur with infections caused by all four *Shigella* species, but is most commonly associated with *S. dysenteriae*, particularly due to the production of shigella toxin. Infections caused by *S. dysenteriae* are more commonly associated with tourism [2]. Gastrointestinal symptoms caused by *Shigella* species range from mild diarrhea for a few days caused by *S. sonnei* to severe diarrhea (bloody stools with mucus), vomiting, and nausea caused by *S. dysenteriae* [5,8].

Although most cases of shigellosis resolve with supportive care, empirical antibiotics have been shown to shorten the duration of illness and reduce stool output and are recommended for immunocompromised patients, patients under 3 months of age, travelers, and patients with severe symptoms [5].

Results and their discussion: When analyzing data from the website of the Public Health Center of Ukraine, the following was revealed: in 2021, 222 cases of shigellosis were detected, in 2022, 223 cases were recorded, in 2023 - 192 cases, and in 2024 - 169 cases of shigellosis. Therefore, when comparing statistics for 2021 and 2022, no significant difference was found. When comparing data for 2023 with 2022, a decrease in the number of cases by 31 cases (16.1%) is noted. This trend can be explained by a decrease in tourism among the population, a lack of mass events, and a decrease in the population of Ukraine since the beginning of the Russian-Ukrainian war. Analysis of incidence rates in 2023 and 2024 indicates a decrease in the number of recorded cases of infection by 23 cases (11.3%).

Conclusion: Shigellosis is a widespread infectious disease. A trend towards a decrease in the incidence of shigellosis has been observed in Ukraine during 2022 to 2024.

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